

ARTISTIC EXPRESSION OF THE IMAGE OF A WOMAN IN ORKHAN POMUK'S NOVEL "THE RED-HAIRED WOMAN"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13834658>

Abstract. *This article examines the novel "The Red-Haired Woman" by Orkhan Pomuk, a famous Turkish novelist, winner of the International Nobel Prize. In particular, the characteristics of the female character in the novel are deeply studied and analyzed.*

Keywords: *novel, analysis, Turkish literature, female image, style.*

The famous Turkish novelist Orkhan Pomuk's novel "The Red-Haired Woman " is one of the rare modern novels published in 2016. The novel is written in a postmodern style, and each character and events have their own connection. Orkhan Pomuk used the unique features of the postmodern novel in his previous novels, according to the writer Nilay Ishiklanan, who analyzed his novel "The Black Book", there are postmodern elements in the novel: a novel within a novel, parody, imitation, police, crime, historical processes often appear in Orkhan Pomuk's novels [2].

In particular, in the works of Orkhan Pomuk, who is considered a modern novelist, special emphasis is placed on the image of a woman. The good and bad qualities of a woman are highlighted in a proportional way. Among the main characters in the novel, more importance is attached to female characters. Literary experts Ozjan Bayrak and Tahsin Yaprak [1], who analyzed the author's other novel "Museum of Innocence", say that in Pomuk's novels there is a novel within a novel or a text within a text, going back, internal monologue, revelation and truth. There are several female characters in the novel. Mrs. Guljihan, who is one of the main characters, has a direct impact on the lives of the main characters. Her red hair, kindness, beautiful smile, and strong love arouse love in the main characters Akin (Jem's father) and Jem. The name of the novel also refers to this woman's hair. Since Orkhan Pomuk is a postmodernist writer, we can find many postmodern elements in his works. It is not difficult to see that the novel is called the woman with red hair, and that the discussion here is more than a woman. *"We were at the station square, the door opened, a middle-aged woman in blue jeans came out. Looking back, she asked in a disgruntled tone "Where did you stand?" When I and my horse came to the open door, a man 5-6 years older than me and a tall and red-haired woman who was the same as his sister came out. This woman had a kind of attractive beauty that was not like anyone else. Before entering the house, the woman looked at me and the horse behind me. I also saw a smile on the round lips of the woman, as if she saw something strange in me or my horse". [3] (İstasyon Meydanı'ndaydık. Bir kapı açıldı. Orta yaşlı, blucinli bir kadın çıktı sokağa. Arkasına dönüp "Nerede kaldınız?" diye seslendi, azarlayıcı bir edayla. Benimle atın şimdi önüne geldiğimiz açık kapıda önce benden beş altı yaş büyük bir genç erkek, sonra onun ablası olabilecek uzun boylu ve kırmızı saçlı bir kadın belirdi. Kadının çok değişik, çekici bir havası vardı.) (KSK,s 25)*

With her feminine tenderness and beauty, this woman enchants Jem, no matter how young she is. Jem, a teenager, soon becomes deeply attached to this woman. He begins to think about this woman day and night. He begins to think about the two of them until he says that it is empty. He believes that in the future, they will marry and live together in an imaginary house. Since the novel

is written in a postmodern style, the lives of the characters are directly connected to one woman through the use of various myths. In the novel, we can find different themes.

Here, emotional qualities such as love, affection, betrayal, friendship, loyalty are reflected in the course of events. Here we can see love and betrayal as the main theme. The main character of the novel, Mrs. Guljihan, has a strong love for Akin. Even after many years, this woman cannot forget Akin and looks for his photo among other people. She is not a light woman in the novel, but proves that a person can be loved strongly despite his absence. She sees her one-time love in Akin's son, Jem. We know it's not easy for single mothers in real life, this woman is raising Jem's son Anwar alone. He finds Akin's reflection in Jem and forms a close relationship with him. *"Actually, you couldn't see his face clearly. Why was she arguing with his mother? I was interested in her claim. Her red hair shone brilliantly in the sunlight. For a minute, she looked at me like an old acquaintance, as if asking what are you doing here, and at that moment our eyes met, as if we were both looking for the same memory from each other, as if asking each other [3].* (Aslında yüzünü tam görememiştim. Annesiyle acaba niye kavga ediyorlardı? Edası etkilemişti beni. Kırmızı saçları ışıktaki tuhaf bir şekilde parlamıştı. Bir an bana eskiden tanıdığı biriymişim gibi, burada ne işin var diye sorar gibi bakmış, tam o sırada göz göze gelmiştik. Sanki ikimiz de bir hatırayı arar, hatta sorgular gibi bakmıştık birbirimize.) (KSK s,26)

We can see that Mrs. Guljihan searched for and found Akin from Jem. In our Eastern nations, we consider a woman's betrayal of her husband as an unforgivable sin. Before evaluating Mrs. Guljihan as a treacherous woman, we should also pay attention to her love for Akin. Jem's father Akin also betrays his wife and son because of this love. For years, Jem's mother has been living unhappily ever since his father's first imprisonment, she tells Jem that your father was a hero and you should be proud of him. However, when his father disappeared for the second time, his mother repeated only one word, saying that she knows what he did. Jem's mother is also a person who deserves to be happy, but she does not see love because of a woman of her husband, Akin. In this way, this woman devotes her whole life to her son Jem. *"But I also noticed that the cause of the silent war between my mother and father was not only politics. Sometimes they were upset for months and did not even speak a word. I don't think they loved each other at all, I could sense that my father loved another woman and that she had a crush on him. Sometimes my mother would tell me about the presence of another woman in a way that I could understand. I forbade myself to think about and remember my mom and dad because the constant wars made me sad" [3].* (Ama babamla annemin aralarındaki sessiz kavgaların tek nedeninin siyaset olmadığını da fark ederdim. Bazan uzun süreler küsüşürler, aralarında neredeyse hiç konuşmazlardı. Belki de birbirlerini sevmiyorlardı. Babamın başka kadınları, pek çok başka kadının da onu sevdiğini seziyordum. Bazan annem başka bir kadın olduğunu benim anlayacağım bir şekilde konuşurdu. Annemle babamın kavgaları beni çok hüznlendirdiği için onları düşünmeyi, hatırlamayı kendime yasaklamıştım) (KSK.s.9)

After this, Akin disappears, leaving his family. Jem is deeply saddened by this. But his mother treats this incident normally and is not interested in her husband's work. It seems that her only goal was to achieve happiness by making her son an educated person. Jem's mother will have a hard time after his father's death.

"During my father's disappearance this time, my mother was not interested in the future of the pharmacy. She didn't talk about the mosque or any other helper, she didn't even tell us what to do with the pharmacy. It also meant to me that this time my father was absent for another reason.

But I couldn't understand what I was thinking" [3]. (Babamın bu son kayboluşunda annem eczaneyle hiç ilgilenmedi. Ne Maciften söz etti, ne başka bir ıranktan, ne de eczanenin ne olacağından. Bu da bana bu sefer babamın başka bir nedenden kaybolduğunu düşündürüyordu. Ama düşünmek dediğimiz şey nedir ki?) (KSK s,10)

In this way, after father's abandonment, he describes his mother's and his situation as mentioned above. At first glance, the image of a woman here is both a woman and a high scheming owner. The life path of every woman in the novel is the same, in fact, they wait for the person they love and dedicate their lives to their children. As long as there is a woman in real life, the meaning of her life will be her child. One of the main characters in the novel is Aisha, Jem's wife. But they try their best to achieve this task. Aisha, like other female characters, is a devoted wife who does not think about betrayal no matter what. Jem always has a positive opinion about his wife. It is said that she loves Jem with all her being, and that she is a pure, kind human being. All the good qualities of women in the whole world seem to be embodied in Aisha. Due to her endless patience and devotion to her husband, she agrees to leave the world without children.

In conclusion, it should be said that the novel contains excerpts from his works about similar aspects of father-son relations in powerful Western and Eastern nations. From this we can know that Orkhan Pomuk is a writer who is well-versed not only in the mysteries of Eastern but also Western nations. In this novel, mainly the personality of the woman is put in the foreground. Feminine femininity can make men love themselves, and at the same time, the high level of their love for their children is revealed. At first glance, the novel seems to have no educational value, but when we read the work from beginning to end, we can clearly see the characteristics of our eastern peoples. In the novel, loyalty to the family is revealed through Jem's mother or Jem's wife, and eternal love is red. The woman with the hair is conveyed to the reader through Mrs. Guljihan. While studying and analyzing the novel, we can see the connection of each character with Mrs. Guljihan, whose name is mentioned in the novel. We also observe another element of the postmodern style in the introduction of stories from the lives of other peoples.

REFERENCES

1. Bayrak, Özcan; Yaprak, Tahsin, “ Ustkurmaca ve görsellik Hissi Bakımından Orhan Pamuk'un Masumiyet Muzesi Romanında Postmodernist unsurlar”, Fırat Ü.Sosyal bilimler Dergisi Elazığ, 2012 C.22 S.1,s.61.
2. Işıklanan, Nilay “Postmodern öğreti ve bir postmodern Roman çözümlemesi: Kara Kitap Orhan Pomuk” Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal bilimler dergisi, eskişehir, 2007 C. 7,S.2, s.419-466
3. Orhan Pamuk” Kırmızı Saçlı Kadın” Yapı Kredi Yayınları - 4560 Edebiyat - 1293 1. baskı: İstanbul, Şubat 2016 S.238
4. Mahfuz Zaric,Batman Üniversitesi “Türk dili ve edebiyatı Postmodernist Yapısal Eleştirisi bağamında Orhan Pamukun Masumiyet muzesi adlı romanı “ 2014. S.78,s.46